

Structural effects of cellulose on hydrolysis and carbonization behavior during hydrothermal treatment

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate, how the morphology of cellulose gets influenced by the hydrolysis and carbonization during hydrothermal treatment at temperatures between 180 – 240 °C. The morphology of cellulose, especially different crystallinity and degree of polymerization, is represented by microcrystalline and α -cellulose. Kinetic analysis is considered as tool to allow the determination of the mechanisms of the two types of celluloses during the hydrothermal process. A kinetic model, in which cellulose was assumed to be hydrolyzed to limited extent, was proposed. Five scenarios were raised as models for pyrolysis of non-hydrolyzed cellulose that formed primary char, along with reaction pathways of hydrolyzable cellulose and its derivatives that latterly form secondary char. The morphologies of solid products were in good agreement with the results of the proposed model.

KEYWORDS

hydrothermal carbonization (HTC), crystallinity, degree of polymerization, kinetic modelling, reaction mechanism.

ABBREVIATIONS

[Cel]	=	concentration of cellulose,	$\text{mol C}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
[S]	=	concentration of sugars,	$\text{mol C}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
[F]	=	concentration of furans,	$\text{mol C}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
[A]	=	concentration of acids,	$\text{mol C}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
[HC]	=	concentration of hydrochar,	$\text{mol C}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
[PC]	=	concentration of pyrochar,	$\text{mol C}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
[R]	=	concentration of residuals,	$\text{mol C}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
t	=	reaction time,	min
A	=	Pre-exponential factor,	min^{-1} or $\text{L}^2\cdot(\text{mol C})^{-2}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$
E_a	=	Activation energy,	$\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$
R	=	Gas constant,	$\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$

TEXT

1. Introduction

Lignocellulosic biomasses, like agricultural residues, energy crops, and forestry wastes, are important resources beyond the field of application as renewable energy to substitute fossil fuels. Moreover, they are also a source for the production of bio-based chemicals. Lignocellulosic biomass is abundant on earth and carbon neutral if it is burned, which validates its sustainability and significant role in bio economy. There are several technologies enabling the conversion of biomass to more valuable products. Such biomass always contains a high moisture content, which is a major challenge due to direct combustion being no feasible idea. Therefore, a hydrothermal treatment, in which hot compressed water at temperatures around 200 °C is involved ¹, is a suitable technology for conversion of wet biomass. Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) is one attractive process that converts biomass into carbonaceous materials. A high versatility of HTC products allows the utilization in many applications like electrode materials in energy storage technologies ², material used as sensor and fuel cell catalyst ³, as well as soil amendments in agriculture ⁴. Furthermore, hydrochar derived from HTC can be applied as solid fuel to replace lignite due to similar heating values ⁵.

Cellulose is frequently used to represent lignocellulosic biomass because it is a primary structural component of the plant cell wall, which makes up 40 – 60 percent dry weight (wt. %) besides hemicellulose and lignin ^{6,7}. It is a polysaccharide linked by β -1,4-glycosidic bonds between D-glucopyranose units forming chains. These chains are linked by hydrogen bonds that are formed between its hydroxyl groups, which results in various orders of crystallinity ⁸. As a result of these inter- and intramolecular forces, cellulose is resistant to various treatments ⁹. Hydrothermal treatment allows hot compressed water to access the inner structures of cellulosic

biomass. Essentially, an arrangement of molecules of cellulose develops its structure into crystalline and amorphous domains. The amorphous fraction in cellulose is more reactive than the crystalline fraction¹⁰. Crystalline-to-amorphous transformation of cellulose takes place when the water penetrates the inner structure at different temperatures depending on their crystallinity¹¹. In fact, crystalline cellulose swells only in supercritical water. Here, the conversion of cellulose from crystalline to amorphous occurs, leading to fast reaction rates to form oligomers¹². In addition, the crystallinity of the unreacted cellulose was almost unchanged by the extent of conversion^{13,14}. Following hydrolysis, dehydration of hydrolyzed C6 and C5 sugars leads to the production of 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) and furfural, respectively¹⁵. These carbon-rich intermediates consecutively polymerize to form secondary char. Whereas, lignin likely forms primary char via solid-to-solid conversion^{16,17}. Both chars are called hydrochar, if they are formed by HTC, despite of their different chemical structure.

Although high numbers of researches investigated in HTC of biomass and cellulose, it is yet unclear how to design operational conditions for HTC processes because the reaction pathway and kinetics are yet largely unknown¹⁸. Until now different kinetic models have been presented for the HTC of cellulose. So far, kinetic analysis was conducted following Arrhenius behavior on an assumption of the first order reaction for hydrolysis and liquid phase reactions (i.e. dehydration, retro-aldol condensation etc.)¹⁹⁻²⁴. Whereas, secondary char formation was found to be favored at a high concentration of HMF, hence the reaction order of the polymerization should be higher than unity²⁵⁻²⁸. A key challenge in this field is that the HTC of cellulose does not only consist of the secondary char formation through dissolved intermediates, but also another parallel reaction pathway, namely the solid-to-solid char formation to so-called primary char²⁹. Falco et al. argued that the solid-to-solid pathway dominates during the HTC of cellulose

due to the presence of large aromatic clusters in the char³⁰. The authors further stated that more furanic-structures should be present similarly to glucose-based char, to prove the presence of secondary char. Their conclusion might be questionable due to the high presence of spherical particles visible in the SEM pictures^{30,31}. These usually are regarded as secondary char³². In another study, it was concluded that spherical particles were dominant if higher acid concentrations were applied, which promoted hydrolysis of the cellulose³³. All in all, it is difficult to analytically distinguish secondary and primary char since both appear as one bulk of char. Current kinetic models handle that aspect with different approaches. Some authors simply neglect secondary char formation and model the primary char formation in terms of a first-order rate equation, which converts cellulose into char^{23,24}. However, first-order might also not completely fit for the HTC of cellulose, since a certain concentration dependency has already been observed³¹. In other studies, hydrochar formation out of real biomasses is solely modeled based on the amount of dissolved compounds²⁷, and in other cases both reaction pathways were included^{25,34,35}.

However, none of those studies have taken structural effects of biomass on kinetic reaction rates into account, which should essentially influence the rate of hydrolysis due to the different crystalline fraction and degree of polymerization (DP) of crystalline and amorphous cellulose. Thus, a kinetic rate analysis of two celluloses representing crystalline (microcrystalline cellulose) and amorphous (α -cellulose) properties was executed. Also, this study is aimed to investigate the hydrolysis and carbonization behavior during HTC with special focus on the solid products. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that parallel determined the reaction kinetics of both primary and secondary char formations of cellulose as feedstock material. Five scenarios for

char production were proposed and the best model was statistically selected as an approach to explain the reaction mechanisms.

2. Results

2.1. Intermediate products

In order to see, whether cellulose degradation happened during the heating period before reaching the target temperature (180 – 240 °C), additional observation at lower temperatures of 140 °C and 160 °C were carried out. Each experimental run started from room temperature and then the reactors were removed from the oven, right after the temperature was reached. By visual observation, each product had no changes in its appearance. Namely, the solid products were as white and liquid effluent was as clear as they were at the beginning. It was confirmed that no degradation had taken place below the temperature of 180 °C by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) of the liquid eluent. No degradation products (sugars, furans, or acids) were detectable.

Low amounts of hydrolyzed products (less than 12 % conversion of cellulose) was observed for both α -cellulose (AC) and microcrystalline cellulose (MC) at 180 °C when the reaction time was long enough. The products became more profound at 200 °C, where higher product yield could be observed from AC than MC. A higher yield of glucose in AC depicts faster hydrolysis of cellulose, which is the rate limiting step. Only very low concentrations of fructose were detected, possibly because of its fast conversion directly after the production. 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) and furfural were produced subsequently from fructose by dehydration. These reaction steps delayed, if employing MC as feedstock. A dramatic change in

cellulose conversion could be seen, if the temperature shifted from 200 °C to 220 °C, where AC and MC completely converted in 180 min and 120 min, respectively. At this temperature, glucose yield become higher in case of MC. At 240 °C, AC and MC started to hydrolyze even before the reaction time was set zero (before the temperature reached 240 °C). However, intermediate products were lower than at 220 °C and at longer reaction time. It is also noteworthy that the major organic acids were formic acid and levulinic acid, where the latter was stable even at longer reaction time. At higher temperatures (200 – 240 °C), the amount of detectable furfurals increased slightly. This was already reported in literature for temperatures close to 200 °C but at higher concentrations and with catalyst. Low concentrations due to either the small degree of conversion of cellulose or the high conversion rate are autocatalyzed by resulting acids whose concentration increases throughout the conversion process ³⁶.

2.2. Solid product characterization

Figure 1 shows differential thermogravimetry (DTG) curves, which demonstrate the relative mass loss of the compound during a temperature change. The peak depicts the main decomposition temperature of the single compound. It shows that raw AC and raw MC decomposed at temperatures of 354 °C and 339 °C, respectively. DTG curves of HTC products from AC and MC treated at 200 °C and 220 °C display shifted peaks to lower temperature range of 320 – 330 °C and the height of the peak decreased with the longer reaction time.

Concurrently, peaks at the temperature around 415 °C, which belong to char appeared when the reaction time was long enough.

In order to quantify the fraction of char products out of unreacted cellulose, an estimation was performed by defining the carbon content of cellulose and char as 44 % and 65 %. Therefore, the carbon, hydrogen and oxygen contents of the product were measured by elemental analysis as

can be found in **Table 1**. The results of elemental analysis are represented by Van-Krevelen diagram in **Figure 2**, which depicts that high severity of operating condition (high temperature and long reaction time) leads to lower O/C and H/C. Spectra derived from Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) shown in **Figure 3** depict peaks of O–H (3300 cm^{-1}), C–H (2900 cm^{-1}), C=O (1740 cm^{-1}), C=C (1600 cm^{-1}), and C–C (1000 cm^{-1}). The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of solid products produced at the longest reaction time of each temperature are shown in comparison with their raw material (AC or MC, respectively) in **Figure 4** and the morphology of solid products is discussed in section 3.1.

2.3. Kinetic analysis

From Eq.1–10, the kinetic rate constants ($k_1 - k_9$) were computed on five different scenarios of pyrochar formation. These calculations are done to mainly proof our possible explanations of the results found. A refinement of these calculations may be necessary to evaluate the predictions. Therefore, the confidence interval of the results is given in the supplementary information in tables 1 and 2. The first assumption is that all the cellulose could have been hydrolyzed and no pyrochar formation has taken place. Hence, the term $k_9f([\text{Cel}])$ in Eq. 1 and Eq. 6 is zero. When pyrolysis is involved, it is important to understand that it is a heterogeneous chemical reaction consisting of several processes, such as nucleation, adsorption, desorption, interfacial reaction, and diffusion³⁷. To simplify the pyrolysis reaction, the assumption for the second to the fifth scenarios are based on the solid-state pyrolysis in a single step. This is according to what was suggested by Antal et al. when they did their research on the pyrolysis of pure Avicel cellulose. Nonetheless, this is only applicable for the solid-to-solid degradation of cellulose because in every other case, the models need to be customized concerning parallel or subsequent reactions³⁸. The second scenario assumed a pseudo-first order reaction for pyrochar, and thus the term

$k_9f([\text{Cel}])$ is $k_9[\text{Cel}]$. While in the third scenario, a nucleation-growth model is considered, which referred from the Prout-Tompkins rate equation that is analogous to a cumulative probability distribution showing sigmoidal behavior. This rate equation infers that the rate of formation of char product depends on both the amount of cellulose and the product itself. The term is hence $k_9[\text{Cel}](1-[\text{Cel}]/3.5)$, where 3.5 is approximated for the carrying capacity, which limits the maximum yield of char. Furthermore, scenarios four and five share a similar idea to the third one, whereas the fourth one takes into account a forcing function³⁹ and the fifth one includes a nucleation parameter, which represents how fast the nucleation is^{37,40-42}. The nucleation parameter was assumed to have a value of 2. All five scenarios are summarized including their quality of fitting represented as root mean square error (RMSE) in **Table 1**.

From **Table 2**, we derived the quality of fitting of the scenario (5)>(4)>(3)>(1)>(2) by a decrease in RMSE. Therefore, the best plots of the scenario (5) compared to experimental data sets are shown in **Figure 5**. As shown, there is no significant difference of product distribution between AC and MC at 180 °C. That is, hydrolysis of celluloses was very slow in both cases, and thus no intermediate compounds of interest and char product were observed. At 200 °C, the model predicted that AC produced hydrochar and partially pyrochar, while MC only produced pyrochar. Hydrolysis of MC might still not be fast enough to produce the hydrochar precursor in liquid phase. At 220 °C, MC seems to hydrolyze better than AC as could be inferred from a higher yield of sugar and furans at earlier reaction time. Consequently, at 240 °C, MC mostly hydrolyzed, and thus the main product was hydrochar. On the other hand, the model predicted that pyrochar was dominant in case of AC.

Table 3 shows the optimized values of the kinetic rate constants ($k_1 - k_9$) from scenario (5), whose pyrochar formation is presumed to be analogous to the nucleation-growth model with

nucleation parameter. It is noteworthy that including the nucleation parameter in the differential rate equations, Eq. 1 and Eq. 6 resulted in unit of k_0 as $L^2 \cdot (\text{mol C})^{-2} \text{min}^{-1}$. The unit of pre-exponential factors is similar to those of the kinetic rate constants. **Table 4** displays the activation energies and the pre-exponential factors obtained from correlation and slope of the Arrhenius plots derived from Eq. 11. These are the plots of the logarithm of the rate constant as a function of the inverse of the absolute temperature. That is, the reaction rate constants at different temperature data points attribute to the activation energy and pre-exponential factor of one specific reaction. The coefficient of determination or R-squared (R^2) expresses how well kinetic rate constants correlate with the reaction temperature.

3. Discussion

3.1. Morphology of the solid products

DTG results in **Figure 1** present the temperature dependent transformation of solid products from both raw materials, AC and MC, for different reaction temperatures and times. The Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curve of raw AC compared to raw MC depicts a broader left-skewed peak inferring diverse structures in AC, i.e. amorphous structure in-between crystalline structure, so-called semi-crystallinity. Therefore, the peak of MC whose structure is more purely crystalline is slightly narrower. After hydrothermal treatment, it is likely that the amorphous regions were destroyed. Consequently, the structure of the products from both AC and MC became more uniform and thus their peaks became narrower and shifted to the left. Here, the peaks represent the conversion of cellulose with respect to the reaction time. An increase of generated peaks at temperatures around 415 °C, which belong to char formation after the

conversion of cellulose, could be observed. The decrease of the cellulose peaks and increase of char peaks are more pronounced at 200 °C for MC. This result correlates well with the finding that more char was produced from MC than AC, which is due to the higher stability against hydrolysis and thus lower reactivity of MC during HTC resulting from its crystalline structure. The structure of MC is the reason for lesser accessibility of water, while the amorphous regions and AC are easily converted.

In **Figure 2**, the Van-Krevelen diagrams of products received from AC and MC conversion show lower O/C and H/C ratios at higher reaction temperature and longer residence time. This is the result of dehydration of cellulose during pyrolysis⁴³ as well as of sugar to HMF⁴⁴. In addition, carbonization is associated by the elimination of water and carbon dioxide, which is the reason for the different compositions of the products⁴⁵. It was assumed that a maximum 4-fold dehydration taking place in one sugar molecule²⁸, which increases the carbon content of hydrochar to 65 %. Beyond this carbon content, decarboxylation further increases the H/C ratio slightly. Decarboxylation could be vaguely observed in case of MC at the most severe conditions of this study, that is the highest temperature and the longest reaction time. The FTIR spectra in **Figure 3** confirm the decarboxylation by lesser intensity of the transmittance peak of the C=O stretching mode ($\tilde{\nu} = 1740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) compared to raw biomass, lower temperatures as well as shorter reaction times. Additionally, dehydration is confirmed by lower peak intensity of the aliphatic O–H stretching mode ($\tilde{\nu} = 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at higher temperatures and longer reaction times. Eliminations of other functional groups are identified by the intensity of the C–H stretch vibration ($\tilde{\nu} = 2900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), C=C stretching ($\tilde{\nu} = 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and C–O stretching mode ($\tilde{\nu} = 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

SEM images in **Figure 4** reveal insightful information about the morphology of char produced from AC and MC, each at different temperatures for the longest reaction time. This is the condition of complete or nearly complete conversion of cellulose. For comparison of AC and MC at the same reaction temperature, SEM images with the same magnification were selected. Surfaces of both, AC and MC, were smooth before hydrothermal treatment. During the treatment at 200 °C, the smoothness of the surface of AC decreased as some deposited objects could be observed in the SEM image. It is noteworthy that unreacted AC remained in the product at this temperature. Furthermore, it is likely that the deposited objects are hydrochar particles that formed from furans in liquid phase. To observe similar objects on the surface of MC after the same treatment at the same conditions is comparatively hard. Instead of that, the solid product broke into smaller pieces. Unlike the product of AC, the product of MC was mostly char since the conversion of MC was nearly completed. Therefore, these small pieces shown in figure 4 are most likely pyrolyzed MC, which, in this work, is stated as pyrochar. These evidences support the prediction in **Figure 5** very well as hydrochar dominates over pyrochar with the existence of unreacted AC while pure pyrochar is produced from MC. This implies that pyrolysis mainly takes place on the crystalline areas because of a comparatively low hydrolysis rate and a more stable structure of MC compared to that of AC. As shown in the SEM images, the products of AC and MC treated at temperatures over 200 °C are similar. That is, spherical-shaped particles accumulated across the whole surface in form of larger particles. Most likely, it can be inferred that the spherical-shaped particles are hydrochar and the larger particles inside are pyrochar. In addition, large loose spherical particles (~3 μm) could be observed beside fiber strings that are covered by very small spheres (~100 nm). This observation is due to the fact that free particles (not settled on pyrochar) can grow through Ostwald-Ripening as well as coalescence²⁸. Whereas

particles that are settled on the surface of the pyrolyzed fiber string are immobilized and cannot grow further, thus remaining very small. Their size is in a range of a few hundred nanometers, which is in agreement with what has been observed as primary nanoparticles in the aggregation of HMF⁴⁶. Nevertheless, some other previous studies discovered a similar morphology of hydrochar produced from a homogeneous reaction, where HMF was an intermediate for the hydrochar formation to receive spherical particles^{26,28}. On the other hand, particles crack due to the release of volatiles from pyrolyzed biomass⁴⁷ but the morphology of pyrochar still resembles original cellulose^{29,48}. This observation also agrees very well with the prediction that both hydrochar and pyrochar were produced with competitive reaction rates.

3.2. Mechanisms of hydrolysis and char formation in liquid phase (hydrochar)

As mentioned in section 2.1, intermediate compounds detected in the liquid phase were evidence of hydrolysis of cellulose. Once cellulose starts to hydrolyze, glucose is released and subsequently isomerized to fructose. The isomerization of glucose and fructose is a reversible reaction, which, at equilibrium, is dominated by glucose. In addition, fructose converts rapidly via dehydration to produce HMF⁴⁹ and thus fructose could hardly be found. Intermediate products reached the highest yield at 220 °C, most likely because, at high temperature, the conversion to hydrochar is preferred.

The kinetic rate constants k_1 , k_2 , and k_5 correlated well with a function of temperature following Arrhenius behavior as depicted in **Table 4**. Activation energy of the hydrolysis of cellulose (reaction associated with k_1) is 137 kJ·mol⁻¹ for AC and 200 kJ·mol⁻¹ for MC. According to some previous literatures, Schwald and Bobleter for example treated cotton cellulose in a batch reactor at temperatures ranged from 245 °C to 275 °C and found that the cellulose hydrolysis is a first-order reaction with an activation energy of 129 kJ·mol⁻¹⁵⁰. It

should be mentioned here that cotton cellulose is analogous to AC because cotton cellulose also exhibits an amorphous structure, as well as regarding their similar crystallinity and DP^{8,51-53}. Therefore, the activation energies reported in the present work and theirs are comparable. Yang et al. reported that the activation energy of MC was 226.5 kJ·mol⁻¹ in a temperature range of 205 – 245 °C⁵⁴. In the same temperature range, their result shows good comparability with ours. Interestingly, the reaction kinetic parameter k_1 of AC was higher than that of MC at temperatures up to 200 °C and then became lower at temperatures above 200 °C. This could be explained by the accessibility of the amorphous regions in AC to water that consequently enhanced the hydrolysis of glycosidic bonds. On the other hand, MC, whose amorphous proportion was removed, rarely had hydrolysable sites available for the access of water and resulted in a lower rate of hydrolysis (close to zero). When the temperature shifted above 200 °C, water could likely better access to crystalline regions of cellulose. Regardless of the crystallinity, the reaction rate of hydrolysis of both, AC and MC, dramatically increased. This could be due to the activation temperature for splitting the glycosidic bonds was reached in this range of temperature. Referring to the lower DP of MC, less hydrolysable bonds in MC could be inferred. Once cellulose was hydrolyzed, there should not be any influences of the structure of cellulose on the reactions in liquid phase. By further assuming equality between AC and MC experiments, activation energies of the reactions related to k_2 and k_5 were determined.

Noteworthy, the reactions to determine k_3 , k_4 , k_6 , k_7 , and k_8 are not the focus of this study because they attribute to the production of acids and unknown residues, which, according to the measurements done, seem to be no part of char production pathways. Thus, the calculated rate constants are included in the supplementary information in table S3 together with the confidence intervals of all the rate constants in tables S1 and S2. Furthermore, the reaction that converts

furans to organic acids (k_4) did not correlate well with different temperatures meaning that Arrhenius behavior is not favored. This is possibly a result of the almost not occurring decomposition of furans to form organic acids, but rather condensation to produce hydrochar and thus a low sensitivity of k_4 could be expected. As such, the low sensitivity might result in wrong interpretation of activation energy and therefore it is not considered.

The formation of hydrochar corresponds to the formation of carbon spheres of which the mechanism of formation is likely a polycondensation of HMF molecules. It is assumed that HMF reacts to 2,5-dioxo-6-hydroxy-hexanal (DHH), which further reacts to an oligomer via aldol-condensation of several HMF molecules^{55,56}. The oligomer precipitates probably due to hydrophobic ripening⁵⁷, and further agglomerates with other oligomers to form spherical particles⁵⁸. Those spheres can further grow through coalescence²⁸. In this course, several water molecules are split off, increasing the carbon content to approx. 65-66 wt.%²⁸. This, in fact, is the minimum carbon content observable in the synthesis of carbon spheres from sugars^{28,33,59-65}, thus also for hydrochar. Sample-dots in the Van-Krevelen plot also indicate that the change in elemental composition from the sugar to the carbon spheres accurately follows dehydration lines at the beginning of the reaction, which is further affiliated by a drift along the decarboxylation lines. These circumstances motivated to develop an adapted HTC model, which is based on an approach presented by Jatzwauk and Schumpe²⁷. As mentioned in the methods section, they assumed that hydrochar has a maximum carbon content of 72 wt.%, and further calculated the fraction of char in the solid phase. In this approach, a solid sample with a carbon content lower than 72 wt.% still contains residual feedstock material. Therefore, their method was developed in the present study by assuming that above 65 wt.% carbon, no feedstock material is left in the solid bulk. In addition, carbonization proceeds via decarboxylation from that point on. It can be

assumed that this calculation procedure, which is derived from the mechanism of formation of hydrochar, can also be applied to the solid-to-solid pathway to form pyrochar. That is because intra-molecular dehydration reactions³⁰, followed by decarboxylation take place in the solid-to-solid pathway similarly to the formation of hydrochar.

3.3. Mechanism of char formation in solid phase (pyrochar)

To investigate more about what the pyrolytic reaction mechanism looks like, the term $k_9 f([Cel]) = k_9 t [Cel] (1 - [Cel]/3.5)^2$ was considered to have an analogy to the Prout-Tompkins equation⁶⁶, which is widely used for the explanation of solid-state kinetics⁶⁷. The Prout-Tompkins equation can also represent an autocatalytic expression, where the final product (Y) catalyzes the reaction start with reactant X:

When assuming α and β are reaction orders, then the rate equation can be written as

$$\frac{d[X]}{dt} = -k[X]^\alpha[Y]^\beta = -k[X]([X]_0 - [X])^\beta \quad \text{or}$$

$$\frac{d[X]}{dt} = -k[X]_0^\beta [X]^\alpha (1 - [X]/[X]_0)^\beta \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Because $[X]_0$ is an initial concentration of a reactant, which is a constant number, the equation can be re-written as

$$\frac{d[X]}{dt} = -k' [X]^\alpha (1 - [X]/[X]_0)^\beta \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The Eq. 14 is analogous to the second term in $k_9 f([Cel]) = k_9 [Cel] (1 - [Cel]/3.5)^2$ where k' is k_9 , α is 1 and β is 2.

Although there was no significant difference between the product yields of pyrochar formation between AC and MC at 180 and 220 °C, interesting predictions from the scenario (5) at 200 °C as depicted in **Figure 5** (b) and (f), and 240 °C as depicted in **Figure 5** (d) and (h) were observed. At 200 °C, AC produced more hydrochar than pyrochar whereas MC produced only pyrochar. At 240 °C, pyrochar was dominant among char products when AC was the starting material. MC mostly hydrolyzed at this temperature as discussed in the previous section, which resulted in dominant hydrochar formation. Char formation via a pyrolytic reaction mechanism in the inner fibers that were not exposed to water gave a good correlation between k_9 and temperature. This led to the conclusion that the pyrolytic reaction in an HTC system obeys the Arrhenius behavior, even though the autocatalytic effect may result in an inconstant kinetic parameter. From the Arrhenius equation in Eq. 11, activation energies (E_a) and pre-exponential factor (A) were calculated and reported in **Table 4**.

It was found that the activation energy of pyrolysis in AC was higher than the one in MC. That means pyrolysis in AC is thermodynamically harder to achieve than MC, which supports the finding that pyrochar was dominant in products from MC, especially at low temperature.

4. Conclusion

The model shown in this study is a closer approach for the fundamental understanding of reactions which take place during the hydrothermal carbonization compared to previous studies. Hydrolysis and carbonization behavior for the calculation of the kinetic reaction rate during hydrothermal treatment of two celluloses are considered. A first order reaction is assumed for all reactions except the formation of pyrochar to simplify the model during computation. In

addition, the kinetic rate analysis considered the formation of char by two parallel pathways. One pathway results in the formation of pyrochar produced from unhydrolyzable cellulose. Both pathways, the one of pyrochar plus that of hydrochar represent a good model of the real behavior of celluloses. In case of pyrochar formation, five different approaches are considered. These approaches allow to understand the formation of the secondary chars based on the initial nucleation-growth model associated with nucleation parameters that represent how fast the reaction proceeded. In addition, the selection of the most suitable pyrochar pathway was calculated and studied statistically. Morphological analysis and the prediction of the kinetic model were consistent.

It was found that, when the temperature was up to 200 °C, the amorphous fraction of cellulose was hydrolyzed, while the crystalline fraction remained resistant to water, thus a higher char yield was observed for microcrystalline cellulose. As the temperature shifted above 220 °C, the effect of crystallinity became less pronounced as demonstrated by less extent of pyrolysis taking place in microcrystalline cellulose. On the contrary, α -cellulose was even more pyrolyzed than microcrystalline cellulose, which suggested that the effect of the degree of polymerization was more significant in terms of hindrance for water to hydrolyze cellulose.

Further investigation on the morphology of hydrochar and pyrochar is necessary in order to be confident about their distinction. In addition, one can further explore on the effects of temperature and pressure of water on its thermal conductivity and heat transfer inside the cellulose structure.

5. Materials and methods

5.1. Materials

Two different types of cellulose (Microcrystalline cellulose (MC) of Merck KGaA and α -cellulose (AC) derived from Sigma Aldrich) were used as received without any prior treatments. MC is typically prepared from AC by treating amorphous regions with acid. As a result, MC has more crystalline fragments and shorter chain lengths while the molecular mass of the repeating unit remains basically the same⁵³. Therefore, MC represents cellulose with high crystallinity and a low DP as opposite to AC.

5.2. Hydrothermal Carbonization (HTC)

HTC experiments were carried out with the experimental setup previously described by Körner et al., which is a 12.2 mL cylindrical stainless steel autoclave (ID = 10 mm, L = 150 mm) equipped with a thermocouple and a temperature logger⁶⁸. 0.85 g of MC or AC with 8.5 mL deionized water (70 % of total reactor volume) was loaded into the autoclave reactor. Then, the reactors were put into a modified gas chromatography oven and heated up to the desired temperature (180 – 240 °C). The pressure of the reactor was in a range of 1.2 – 3.7 MPa corresponding to the amount of water inside the reactor and reaction temperatures. After reaching the reaction temperature, reaction times between zero min and 240 min were recorded. In order to see further conversion of cellulose at 200 °C, the reaction time was extended to 480 min. The reaction was terminated by quenching the autoclave reactors in a cold-water bath. Solid and liquid products were separated by vacuum filtration using 0.45 μ m nylon membrane filter (Whatman). Solid particles were washed with deionized water and dried in an oven at 105 °C overnight.

5.3. Analysis

5.3.1. Solid phase

Dried solid products were removed from the membrane papers and ground to ensure the homogeneity of the sample prior to elemental analysis using an Elemental Analyser (Euro EA-CHNSO, Hekatech). These solid products are simplified as remaining cellulose and char in the present work due to the methodology of the kinetic studies, thus, the preparation of the kinetic model is simplified. While the real composition of the solid products was therefore not determined in the present study, proof was given that these consist of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons⁶⁹. Their determination was carried out in an indirect method adapted from the ones described in the work of Jatzwauck and Schumpe²⁷. They assumed that the carbon content of the solid phase is the mean value between the mass fraction of cellulose having a carbon content of 44 wt.% and hydrochar with 72 wt.%. This procedure can be improved by considering the fact that so-called carbon spheres (secondary char), produced from monomeric sugars, commonly have a carbon content of 65-66 %^{28,33,59-65}, which most likely arises from a 4-fold dehydration of a monosaccharide²⁸. Therefore, it can be assumed that, once the solid phase after HTC (of cellulose) reached a carbon content of 65 %, no original cellulose is present anymore. A further rise in carbon content is only possible through solid-to-solid reactions, such as decarboxylation.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of raw material and product samples was carried out using a STA 449 F5 thermogravimetric balance from NETZSCH-Gerätebau GmbH (Ahlden, Germany). Samples of around 15 mg were weighed out into Al₂O₃ crucibles to fulfill the regulation of the International Confederation for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry⁷⁰. They propose a sample mass times heating rate of less than 100 mg °C·min⁻¹ to avoid limitations of heat and mass transfer. The initial moisture content was removed by heating samples up from

room temperature to 105 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min over 10 min. Subsequently, the samples were heated up to 900 °C with a constant heating rate of 10 °C/min under a N₂ flow of 100 mL/min.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was performed using Bruker ALPHA II PLATINUM-ATR (Germany). Wave numbers in between 400 cm⁻¹ and 4000 cm⁻¹ were scanned by averaging 24 scans. The background was recorded and subtracted from the measurements of raw material and HTC products to prevent from signals of the surrounding and get a smooth baseline.

A scanning electron microscope (SEM; Inspect F50; FEI, Eindhoven, Netherlands) analysis was conducted in order to study the morphological features of raw material and selected solid samples. Each sample was attached to the metal mounting of the SEM using carbon double-sided tape. All of the samples were coated with Pd (Leica EM ACE200 coater).

5.3.2. Liquid phase

Liquid products were obtained after vacuum filtration without dilution. The identification of specific intermediate products in the liquid phase, as specified later, was done by a high-performance liquid chromatograph (HPLC, Shimadzu) equipped with a refractive index detector (RID) and a BioRad Aminex column (300×7.8 mm I.D.). The analytical conditions were as following: 4 mM aqueous sulfuric acid solution as mobile eluent, a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min and an oven temperature of 35 °C.

5.4. Kinetic model

The kinetic model of the HTC of cellulose is proposed and expressed in **Scheme 1**. From this point on, the primary char and secondary char are stated as “pyrochar” and “hydrochar”,

respectively, to reflect the mechanisms they are produced with. The parts of the cellulose that are considered as non-hydrolyzable during HTC are called pyrochar (PC). This is due to the solid-to-solid mechanism they are converted by, which is similar to pyrolysis previously described by several authors like Ld et al.⁷¹ as well as Antal et al.^{71,72}. However, the present mechanism for the solid-to-solid conversion in this study is more likely comparable to the resulting solids of wet torrefaction or low temperature pyrolysis⁷³. Hydrochar (HC) is the solid formed by secondary char reactions during the hydrolysis of cellulose to intermediates and the simultaneous dehydration, decarboxylation and polymerization reaction, as previous studies showed^{74,75}. Such low torrefaction temperature is possible here because water is a very good heat transfer medium due to its high thermal conductivity compared to air, which is the medium in conventional pyrolysis. Additionally, the decomposition of the cellulose during HTC occurs at a lower temperature compared to dry torrefaction because it is performed in water under subcritical conditions⁷⁶.

Importantly, the amount of solved intermediates was comparatively low to solid products. Therefore, the products that have similar functional groups are lumped together for better evaluation. That is, glucose and fructose are lumped into sugar (S), HMF and furfural are lumped into furans (F), and all the detectable organic acids are lumped into acids (A). In detail, this model was proposed based on the knowledge that cellulose was partially hydrolyzed to oligomers and consequently glucose is produced^{75,77,78}. It was not possible to quantify the oligomers; thus, they were implicitly included in the residuals (R1). In fact, the kinetic rate constant of the conversion of cellulose (Cel) to oligomers (R1) differs from that of oligomers to glucose⁷⁹. Presumably, the change should not be significant because both conversions are hydrolyses that are similarly a cleavage of the glycosidic bonds. This was supported by the idea

of Calvini et al. who proposed the most accurate way to describe the degradation of cellulose would be a sum of first order reactions. Beyond that, they also reported that a simplification should be made by the approximation of quite equal reaction rates. Therefore, these two consecutive conversions share the same kinetic rate constant (k_1). Glucose further isomerizes to fructose^{80,81}, from which consequently HMF and furfural are generated by dehydration of fructose⁸². Hydrochar is formed from polymerization of HMF and furfural, which is supposed to have a reaction order greater than one according to evidence that char production increased with substrate concentration observed by many previous studies²⁵⁻²⁸. However, it is not reasonable to assume a higher reaction order for hydrochar formation in this work because the hydrochar was produced from low concentration intermediates, not from the initial substrate. In other words, the concentration of char precursors is not a controllable variable hence reaction order should not be considered as a variable in the model. Furthermore, a significant determination of the reaction order wasn't possible because only one starting concentration of cellulose was used. Thus, every reaction order between 1 and 2 is possible to fit the data together with the corresponding rate constant. It may also cause overfitting by assuming too many variables. In addition, organic acids are well-known as byproducts in hydrothermal processes of lignocellulosic biomass⁸³. Levulinic acid is the main decomposition product of HMF^{68,84}, while the other light carboxylic acids (formic, acetic, lactic acids) are formed as degradation products of sugars⁷⁵. Despite that, organic acids possibly gasify. Those gas products were negligible because the operating conditions in this study were not severe enough for the gasification to occur and therefore did not produce a significant amount of gas. Regarding that not all compounds could be identified and quantified as well as interconnected liquid and solid reactions are taken into consideration, it is necessary to perform the calculation on a basis of mole carbon atoms instead of the mole of each

single compound. In addition, the concentration of cellulose does not exist because cellulose particles actually just submerge in the water without dissolving. Here, the concentration of cellulose means the total mole carbon atoms of cellulose molecules per specific volume. All the HPLC analysis were performed in mol C·L⁻¹ to use the same unit for both, liquid and solid products, because the carbon balance is easy to calculate for both. Regarding this, the carbon balance of the liquids is closed due to separation of only water during the conversion, thus the rate constants are comparable with both units. Furthermore, the activation energy of the liquid samples could be calculated by using mol C·L⁻¹ instead of g·L⁻¹. The unidentified compounds were quantified as residuals, which make up the missing percentages to even the carbon balance to 100 %. The residuals can be degradation products of sugars, furans, and acids as specified as R2, R3, and R4, respectively.

To fit the rate equations, the results of HPLC and EA were used. Assuming the first order for all reactions except pyrochar formation, reaction rate equations for each compound were derived. That is, the change of concentration of reactants or products with time is proportional to concentration of the reactants.

$$\frac{d[Cel]}{dt} = -k_1[Cel] - k_9f([Cel]) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\frac{d[S]}{dt} = k_1[R1] - (k_2 + k_3 + k_6)[S] \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\frac{d[F]}{dt} = k_2[S] - (k_4 + k_5 + k_7)[F] \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$\frac{d[A]}{dt} = k_3[S] + k_4[F] - k_8[A] \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\frac{d[HC]}{dt} = k_5[F] \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$\frac{d[PC]}{dt} = k_9 f([Cel]) \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\frac{d[R1]}{dt} = k_1 [Cel] - k_1 [R1] \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$\frac{d[R2]}{dt} = k_6 [S] \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$\frac{d[R3]}{dt} = k_7 [F] \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$\frac{d[R4]}{dt} = k_8 [A] \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

The kinetic rate constants ($k_1 - k_9$) were computed by MATLAB R2018b⁸⁵ using lsqnonlin function to minimize non-linear least square errors of experimental and predicted values. The term $k_9 f([Cel])$ represents solid-state conversion of cellulose, where $f([Cel])$ is a function of the concentration of cellulose substrate. This term was yet unknown in its pattern, and therefore different theories and mathematical models were applied until the best curve fitting was obtained. The selected model was then used to explain possible mechanisms in the solid-to-solid conversion. Afterwards, the Arrhenius behavior is considered to determine the activation energy (E_a) and pre-exponential factor (A) of the reactions of interest. In general, chemical reactions are limited to the number of molecules hitting each other, whose energy is larger than E_A , which is $\sim \frac{E_a}{RT}$. This ratio and thus the number of molecules reacting, has a comparatively low dependence on the temperature (T). In a nutshell, this means that the kinetic rate constant is dependent on the negative exponential of the temperature, thus E_a and A are specific constants for each reaction. According to Arrhenius equation (Eq.13), E_a and A were determined by plotting each kinetic rate constant against an inversed absolute temperature ($1/T$).

$$k = A \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

The accuracy of fitting is represented by root mean square error (RMSE), which formulates as expressed in Eq.14.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(\text{predicted value} - \text{actual value})^2}{\text{number of experimental runs}}} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

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Figure 4. SEM images of AC, MC and their solid products at different temperatures and the longest reaction time observed in each condition (Magnification 12000x for raw materials a) AC and e) MC, 6000x for b) AC 200 °C and f) MC 200 °C, and 24000x for c) AC 220 °C d) AC 240 °C g) MC 220 °C h) MC 240 °C).

Figure 5. Concentration of products from AC at a) 180 °C b) 200 °C c) 220 °C d) 240 °C and from MC at e) 180 °C f) 200 °C g) 220 °C h) 240 °C as a function of reaction time (○: Cellulose, □: Sugars, * : Furans, ◇: Char, solid lines: model predicted yield, dot lines: predicted pyrochar, and dash lines: predicted hydrochar).

Table 1. Elemental content of solid product from HTC of AC and MC at different temperature and reaction time.

Temp [°C]	Time [min]	AC			MC		
		C	H	O	C	H	O
180	0	42.47	6.78	50.76	43.30	6.79	49.91
	15	42.68	6.82	50.50	43.26	6.93	49.81
	30	42.63	6.83	50.55	43.16	6.61	50.24
	45	43.37	6.96	49.68	43.21	6.72	50.07
	60	42.51	6.78	50.70	43.37	6.76	49.87
	120	42.57	6.89	50.55	43.42	6.78	49.80
	180	42.45	6.80	50.75	43.40	6.77	49.84
	240	42.80	6.78	50.42	42.69	6.82	50.49
200	0	41.74	6.42	51.85	42.99	6.86	50.15
	15	42.00	6.58	51.42	42.74	6.67	50.59
	30	41.98	6.46	51.56	43.72	6.79	49.48
	45	41.98	6.35	51.67	42.55	6.71	50.74
	60	41.24	6.13	52.63	43.09	6.80	50.11
	120	42.28	6.18	51.55	43.30	6.61	50.09
	180	43.10	6.30	50.60	44.07	6.75	49.19
	240	45.74	6.18	48.08	46.35	6.41	47.24
	300	47.87	6.14	45.99	48.49	5.92	45.60
	360	49.14	5.98	44.89	53.45	5.37	41.18
220	0	50.10	5.73	44.18	62.39	4.71	32.90
	480	52.77	5.37	41.87	63.54	4.57	31.89
	0	42.79	6.82	50.39	42.95	6.85	50.20
	15	44.51	7.06	48.44	42.90	6.83	50.28
	30	43.87	6.63	49.49	43.30	6.77	49.93
	45	45.20	6.60	48.20	45.51	6.62	47.87
	60	47.59	6.43	45.98	50.33	6.21	43.47
	120	60.16	5.23	34.61	65.92	4.28	29.80
	180	65.78	4.86	29.36	67.21	4.30	28.49
	240	67.55	4.66	27.80	67.87	4.48	27.66
240	0	43.13	6.77	50.09	40.57	6.31	53.12
	15	50.15	6.30	43.55	58.96	4.68	36.36
	30	64.76	5.01	30.23	66.74	4.30	28.96
	45	66.36	4.46	29.18	66.31	4.08	29.61
	60	65.95	4.03	30.02	69.24	4.47	26.29
	120	68.97	4.31	26.72	69.19	4.46	26.35
	180	67.41	4.33	28.26	69.45	4.46	26.09
	240	67.00	4.11	28.88	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 2. Summary of five scenarios for pyrochar formation mechanisms and RMSE of each scenario.

Scenario	Equation	RMSE [mol C·L ⁻¹]	
		AC	MC
(1) No pyrochar	$k_9f([Cel]) = 0$	6.1723	7.1390
(2) Pseudo-first order	$k_9f([Cel]) = k_9[Cel]$	6.2638	6.9010
(3) Nucleation-growth	$k_9f([Cel]) = k_9[Cel](1 - [Cel]/3.5)$	5.3521	5.5260
(4) Nucleation-growth with forcing function	$k_9f([Cel]) = k_9t[Cel](1 - [Cel]/3.5)$	5.7203	5.1095
(5) Nucleation-growth with nucleation parameter	$k_9f([Cel]) = k_9[Cel](1 - [Cel]/3.5)^2$	5.1971	4.6902

Table 3. Reaction rate constants of proposed scheme in AC and MC at different temperatures.

Reaction rate constant*	AC				MC			
	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C
k ₁	4.85E-04	1.31E-03	7.79E-03	3.03E-02	2.63E-04	1.39E-03	1.12E-02	1.35E-02
k ₂	2.27E+01	1.40E-02	8.53E-02	2.76E-01	2.96E-02	1.75E-02	2.81E-02	1.30E-01
k ₅	2.50E-14	7.03E-09	1.98E-02	4.24E-02	3.78E-14	2.59E-14	2.86E-02	1.50E-01
k ₉	2.23E-06	9.05E-03	3.69E-02	1.44E-01	1.10E-05	1.56E-02	4.61E-02	7.80E-01

* The unit of kinetic rate constant is min⁻¹ for **k₁-k₅** and L²(mol C)⁻²min⁻¹ for **k₉**.

Table 4. Activation energy and pre-exponential factor of specific reactions in the proposed scheme.

Reaction	E_a [J·mol ⁻¹]	A [*]	R^2 [-]
k _{1_AC}	1.37E+05	2.25E+12	0.98
k _{1_MC}	2.00E+05	2.44E+19	0.98
k ₂	1.26E+05	1.09E+12	0.87
k ₅	1.27E+05	6.83E+11	0.63
k _{9_AC}	1.39E+05	2.22E+13	0.97
k _{9_MC}	8.16E+04	1.70E+07	1.00

* Units of pre-exponential factors (A) are similar to those of associated kinetic reaction constants (k)

Scheme 1. Proposed reaction pathway of hydrothermal conversion of cellulose.

Figure 1. DTG curves of solid products comparing to raw material (AC or MC) at different temperatures and reaction times (a) AC 200 °C, b) AC 220 °C, c) MC 200 °C, d) MC 220 °C).

Figure 2. Van-Krevelen diagram of solid products from HTC of a) AC and b) MC.

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of solid products comparing to raw material (AC or MC) at different temperatures and reaction times (a) AC 200 °C, b) AC 220 °C, c) AC 240 °C, d) MC 200 °C, e) MC 220 °C, f) MC 240 °C).

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* Reaction time of b) AC200 and f) MC200 is longer than the others.

** Full plots that include acids and other compounds are available in SI material.

Figure 5. Concentration of products from AC at a) 180 °C b) 200 °C c) 220 °C d) 240 °C and from MC at e) 180 °C f) 200 °C g) 220 °C h) 240 °C as a function of reaction time (○: Cellulose, □: Sugars, * : Furans, ◇: Char, solid lines: model predicted yield, dot lines: predicted pyrochar, and dash lines: predicted hydrochar).

ABSTRACT GRAPHIC (For Table of Contents Use Only)

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Supplementary Material

Table S1. Predicted reaction rate constants of proposed reaction scheme for AC with their 95 % confidence interval

Reaction rate constant*	AC				± 95 % confidence interval			
	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C
k ₁	4.85E-04	1.31E-03	7.79E-03	3.03E-02	1.55E-04	3.28E-04	1.43E-03	7.14E-03
k ₂	2.27E+01	1.40E-02	8.53E-02	2.76E-01	8.20E+02	1.52E-01	2.40E-01	3.21E-01
k ₃	2.82E-02	2.88E-07	6.36E-02	4.16E-02	3.41E+02	1.79E-01	2.11E-01	1.39E-01
k ₄	6.57E-11	1.20E-02	6.59E-11	2.25E-14	7.33E+04	2.92E-01	1.17E-01	4.60E-01
k ₅	2.50E-14	7.03E-09	1.98E-02	4.24E-02	3.67E-02	1.73E-02	1.81E-02	2.25E-02
k ₆	4.12E-14	2.83E-14	4.36E-10	6.61E-09	3.51E+02	1.66E-01	1.77E-01	1.90E-01
k ₇	4.08E-14	2.97E-14	8.74E-10	4.05E-02	7.33E+04	2.95E-01	1.20E-01	6.64E-01
k ₈	4.04E-14	1.01E-08	3.63E-03	1.14E-03	5.80E+07	6.21E-02	4.50E-02	4.66E-02
k ₉	2.23E-06	9.05E-03	3.69E-02	1.44E-01	9.81E-02	5.04E-03	1.32E-02	3.00E-02

* The unit of kinetic rate constant is min⁻¹ for **k₁-k₈** and L²(mol C)⁻²min⁻¹ for **k₉**.

Table S2. Predicted reaction rate constants of proposed reaction scheme for MC with their 95 % confidence interval

Reaction rate constant*	MC				± 95% confidence interval			
	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C
k ₁	2.63E-04	1.39E-03	1.12E-02	1.35E-01	2.37E-04	2.50E-04	2.16E-03	4.49E-01
k ₂	2.96E-02	1.75E-02	2.81E-02	1.30E-01	9.15E-01	4.01E-01	5.70E-02	7.56E-01
k ₃	4.89E-09	6.85E-11	2.35E-02	3.69E-02	1.14E-03	3.73E-01	6.22E-02	4.82E-01
k ₄	4.32E-14	2.82E-02	2.11E-11	5.93E-14	3.93E+01	7.01E-01	1.26E-01	5.79E-01
k ₅	3.78E-14	2.59E-14	2.86E-02	1.50E-01	1.49E-01	2.21E-02	3.07E-02	6.36E-01
k ₆	6.50E-14	1.47E-10	5.22E-13	4.95E-02	7.80E-01	2.40E-01	6.55E-02	7.26E-01
k ₇	2.79E-14	2.56E-14	2.12E-12	2.34E-10	3.92E+01	5.42E-01	1.32E-01	8.65E-01
k ₈	2.46E+00	2.56E-14	3.55E-03	5.78E-04	2.99E+03	2.60E-02	2.61E-02	2.29E-01
k ₉	1.10E-05	1.56E-02	4.61E-02	7.80E-02	3.04E-01	3.97E-03	2.09E-02	7.82E-01

* The unit of kinetic rate constant is min⁻¹ for **k₁-k₈** and L²(mol C)⁻²min⁻¹ for **k₉**.

Table S3. Missing reaction rate constants of proposed scheme in AC and MC at different temperatures.

Reaction rate constant*	AC				MC			
	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C
k ₃	2.82E-02	2.88E-07	6.36E-02	4.16E-02	4.89E-09	6.85E-11	2.35E-02	3.69E-01
k ₄	6.57E-11	1.20E-02	6.59E-11	2.25E-14	4.32E-14	2.82E-02	2.11E-11	5.93E-01
k ₆	4.12E-14	2.83E-14	4.36E-10	6.61E-09	6.50E-14	1.47E-10	5.22E-13	4.95E-01
k ₇	4.08E-14	2.97E-14	8.74E-10	4.05E-02	2.79E-14	2.56E-14	2.12E-12	2.34E-01
k ₈	4.04E-14	1.01E-08	3.63E-03	1.14E-03	2.46E+00	2.56E-14	3.55E-03	5.78E-01

* The unit of kinetic rate constant is min⁻¹ for **k₃-k₈**.

Figure S1. Arrhenius plots of kinetic rate constants (k)

Figure S2. Concentration of products from AC at a) 180 °C b) 200 °C c) 220 °C d) 240 °C and from MC at e) 180 °C f) 200 °C g) 220 °C h) 240 °C as a function of reaction time (○: Cellulose, □: Sugars, * : Furans, △: Acids, ◇: Char, +: Residues, solid lines: model predicted yield, dot lines: predicted pyrochar, and dash lines: predicted hydrochar).